

ISic0321

Mosaic inscription

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2017.07.01

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Each word is placed in a tabula ansata, held in the hands of a pair of facing small naked male figures

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Utere feliciter

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491530

EDR 141142

EDCS 21900359

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus*

Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.7037 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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